

**List of plant-feeding sawflies by their host plant associations in Hungary
(Hymenoptera: Symphyta)**

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Abstract – A list of host plants and associated plant-feeding species of wasps (Hymenoptera) belonging to the paraphyletic group Symphyta (sawflies and their allies) is presented based predominantly on the author's handbooks published in the book series Fauna Hungariae. The tribe Nematini (Tenthredinidae) is excluded. 420 host plant taxa and the associated 1115 host records of sawflies are listed.

Key words – Fauna Hungariae, compilation, host plant records

INTRODUCTION

The presented list of host plants and their associated species of Hymenoptera formerly frequently placed into the paraphyletic group Symphyta (sawflies and their allies), inspired by ENSLIN (1918), is a compilation based predominantly on the author's handbooks published in the book series Fauna Hungariae (MÓCZÁR & ZOMBORI 1973, ZOMBORI 1982, 1990, 2016, 2022*a*). Nevertheless, the works of TAEGER *et al.* (1998), ROLLER & HARIS (2008), and ZOMBORI (2022*b*, 2023) were also considered. The author made similar attempts in the indices of his latest issues of Fauna Hungariae (ZOMBORI 2016, 2022*a*) by listing the host plants and sawflies. Some host plant associations of certain sawfly species were not indicated in issues of Fauna Hungariae, but only in two recent works by ZOMBORI (2022*b*, 2023); those are marked with an asterisk (*) within the list.

Nomenclature of sawflies follows the above-mentioned sources. The tribe Nematini (Tenthredinidae) is excluded due to the fact that the pertaining genera have not been treated in the author's Fauna Hungariae handbooks. The family Orussidae is also omitted due to the parasitic lifestyle of its members.

Nomenclature of host plants follows mainly SOÓ & KÁRPÁTI (1968), with some necessary updates based on Euro+Med PlantBase*. In several cases only genus- (or rarely only family-) group names of host plants are given, indicating

* <http://www.europlusmed.org> (accessed 1 July 2025)

the lack of more precise identity of the host plant. It is worth noting that host plant taxa include native and non-native, cultivated species (either for food or ornamental purposes). Some listed plant taxa are quite rare in Hungary, but are more common not far from the present borders of the country; following the principles of the author's issues published in *Fauna Hungariae* (MÓCZÁR & ZOMBORI 1973, ZOMBORI 1982, 1990, 2016, 2022a), these are also considered if previous literature data confirmed the association with sawfly species present in Hungary. Taxa are listed in alphabetic order by host plants; their associated sawflies are also listed alphabetically.

The known host plant associations of sawflies, listed by the host plants, may help the identifications of sawflies, especially their larvae collected from the host plants.

LIST OF HOST PLANT AND SAWFLY TAXA

- Abies alba* Mill. – *Pleroneura dahlii* (Hartig, 1837), *Sirex juvencus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Sirex noctilio* Fabricius, 1773, *Urocerus augur* (Klug, 1803), *Urocerus gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Acer L.* – *Xiphydria longicollis* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Acer campestre L.* – *Heterarthrus aceris* (Kaltenbach, 1856), *Heterarthrus healyi* Altenhofer et Zombori, 1987*, *Heterarthrus leucomelas* (Klug, 1818), *Hinatara nigripes* (Konow, 1907), *Messa hortulana* (Klug, 1818), *Tremex magus* (Fabricius, 1787)
- Acer platanoides L.* – *Heterarthrus aceris* (Kaltenbach, 1856), *Hinatara recta* (Thomson, 1871), *Messa hortulana* (Klug, 1818), *Pamphilius aurantiacus* (Giraud, 1857), *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Acer pseudoplatanus L.* – *Heterarthrus aceris* (Kaltenbach, 1856), *Heterarthrus cuneifrons* Altenhofer et Zombori, 1987*, *Heterarthrus healyi* Altenhofer et Zombori, 1987*, *Heterarthrus leucomelas* (Klug, 1818), *Heterarthrus wuestneii* (Konow, 1905)*, *Hinatara excisa* (Konow, 1885), *Hinatara nigripes* (Konow, 1907), *Pamphilius neglectus* (Zaddach, 1859)
- Aconitum L.* – *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817
- Adoxa moschatellina L.* – *Dicrostema gracilicorne* (Zaddach, 1859), *Sciapteryx consobrina* (Klug, 1816)
- Aegopodium podagraria L.* – *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo bifasciata* Müller, 1766, *Tenthredo campestris* Linnaeus, 1758
- Agrimonia L.* – *Fenella nigrita* Westwood, 1839*, *Hartigia xanthostoma* (Eversmann, 1847)
- Agrimonia eupatoria L.* – *Fenella nigrita* Westwood, 1840, *Hartigia linearis* (Schrank, 1781), *Macrophya rufipes* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)

- Agrostis* L. – *Tenthredopsis friesei* (Konow, 1884), *Tenthredopsis litterata* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Agrostis capillaris* L. – *Tenthredopsis tischbeinii* (Fivaldszky, 1876)
- Agrostis stolonifera* L. – *Tenthredopsis tischbeinii* (Fivaldszky, 1876)
- Aira* L. – *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis tessellata* (Klug, 1817)
- Ajuga reptans* L. – *Athalia cordata* Lepeletier, 1823
- Alchemilla* L. – *Pachyprotasis nigronotata* (Kriechbaumer, 1874)
- Alchemilla monticola* Opiz. – *Claremontia tenuicornis* (Klug, 1816), *Emphytus calceatus* (Klug, 1818)
- Alliaria petiolata* (M. B.) Cavara et Grande – *Athalia liberta* (Klug, 1815)
- Alnus* Mill. – *Abia connata* (Schrank, 1776), *Atomostethus ephippium* (Panzer, 1798), *Eriocampa umbratica* (Klug, 1816), *Hemichroa australis* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Hemichroa crocea* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Hemichroa monticola* (Ermolenko, 1960), *Macrophya duodecimpunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Macrophya montana* (Scopoli, 1763), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Xiphydria camelus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Xiphydria longicollis* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. – *Eriocampa ovata* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Fenusa dohrnii* (Tischbein, 1846), *Heterarthrus vagans* (Fallén, 1808), *Monsoma pulveratum* (Retzius, 1783), *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Alnus incana* (L.) Mnch. – *Eriocampa ovata* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Fenusa dohrnii* (Tischbein, 1846), *Monsoma pulveratum* (Retzius, 1783), *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Pamphilius vafer* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Alnus viridis* (Chaix.) DC. – *Fenusa pusilla* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Heterarthrus fruticicolum* Ermolenko, 1960, *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Scolioneura betuleti* (Klug, 1816), *Tenthredo velox* Fabricius, 1798
- Alopecurus* L. – *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793)
- Amelanchier* Medic. – *Hoplocampa plagiata* (Klug, 1816)
- Amelanchier ovalis* Medic. – *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Anagallis arvensis* L. – *Monostegia abdominalis* (Fabricius, 1798)
- Anemone* L. – *Sciapteryx consobrina* (Klug, 1816), *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Anemone nemorosa* L. – *Endophytus anemones* (Hering, 1924)
- Anemone sylvestris* L. – *Pseudodineura heringi* (Enslin, 1921)
- Angelica* L. – *Tenthredo fagi* Panzer, 1798
- Angelica archangelica* L. – *Tenthredo crassa* Scopoli, 1763
- Angelica sylvestris* L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Anthirrhinum* L. – *Athalia cordata* Lepeletier, 1823, *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Anthriscus sylvestris* (L.) Hoffm. – *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh. – *Athalia liberta* (Klug, 1815)

- Arctium lappa* L. – *Athalia circularis* (Klug, 1815), *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Armoracia rusticana* G. Gaertn. et al. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Arrhenatherum elatius* (L.) Presl. – *Calameuta filiformis* (Eversmann, 1847), *Tenthredopsis sordida* (Klug, 1817)
- Artemisia* L. – *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Artemisia vulgaris* L. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)*
- Aster amellus* L. – *Pachyprotasis simulans* (Klug, 1817)
- Aster novi-belgii* L. – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Athyrium filix-femina* (L.) Roth. – *Aneugmenus coronatus* (Klug, 1818), *Blasticotoma filiceti* Klug, 1834, *Heptamelus ochroleucus* (Stephens, 1835), *Stromboceros delicatulus* (Fallén, 1808), *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Thrinax macula* (Klug, 1817), *Thrinax mixta* (Klug, 1814)
- Atropa belladonna* L. – *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912)
- Avena* L. – *Dolerus haematodes* (Schrank, 1781)
- Barbarea* Beckm. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Berberis vulgaris* L. – *Arge berberidis* Schrank, 1802
- Betula* L. – *Allantus togatus* (Panzer, 1801), *Arge clavicornis* Fabricius, 1781, *Arge dimidiata* (Fallén, 1808), *Arge pullata* (Zaddach, 1859), *Arge ustulata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Caliroa varipes* (Klug, 1816), *Cimbex femoratus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Dineura virididorsata* (Retzius, 1783), *Emphytus cingillum* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus cingulatus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Hemichroa australis* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Hemichroa crocea* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Heterarthrus nemoratus* (Fallén, 1808), *Parataxonus candidatus* (Fallén, 1808), *Pseudoxiphydria betulae* (Enslin, 1911), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Tremex fuscicornis* (Fabricius, 1787), *Trichiosoma latreillei* Leach, 1817, *Trichiosoma lucorum* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Xiphydria longicollis* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Betula pendula* Roth – *Fenusia pusilla* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Messa nana* (Klug, 1816), *Pamphilius pallipes* (Zetterstedt, 1838), *Pamphilius varius* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Profenusia thomsoni* (Konow, 1886), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Scolioneura betuleti* (Klug, 1816), *Scolioneura nigricans* (Klug, 1816), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Betula pubescens* Ehrh. – *Fenusia pusilla* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Messa nana* (Klug, 1816), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Profenusia thomsoni* (Konow, 1886), *Scolioneura nigricans* (Klug, 1816)
- Blechnum spicant* (L.) Sm. – *Heptamelus ochroleucus* (Stephens, 1835)
- Brachypodium* P. B. – *Tenthredo maculata* Geoffroy, 1785
- Brachypodium sylvaticum* (Huds.) R. et Sch. – *Tenthredopsis excisa* (Thomson, 1870), *Tenthredopsis tarsata* (Fabricius, 104), *Tenthredopsis tischbeinii* (Frivaldszky, 1876)

- Brassica* L. – *Athalia glabricollis* (Thomson, 1870), *Athalia lugens* (Klug, 1813)
Brassica napus L. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
Brassica nigra (L.) Koch. – *Elinora flaveola* (Gmelin, 1790)
Brassica oleracea L. – *Elinora flaveola* (Gmelin, 1790)
Brassica rapa L. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Bupleurum falcatum L. – *Tenthredo sulphuripes* (Kriechbaumer, 1869)
Calamagrostis Roth – *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredopsis sordida* (Klug, 1817)
Calamagrostis epigejos (L.) Roth – *Calameuta filiformis* (Eversmann, 1847), *Tenthredopsis friesei* (Konow, 1884), *Tenthredopsis litterata* (Geoffroy, 1785)
Calamagrostis arundinacea (L.) Roth – *Tenthredopsis friesei* (Konow, 1884)
Cardamine L. – *Cuneala koehleri* (Gmelin, 1790)
Cardamine hirsuta L. – *Athalia liberta* (Klug, 1815)
Carduus L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Carex L. – *Brachythops flavens* (Klug, 1816), *Dolerus gibbosus* Hartig, 1827, *Dolerus haematodes* (Schrank, 1781), *Macrophya duodecimpunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1783), *Selandria sixii* Vollenhoven, 1858, *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Carex lasiocarpa Ehrh. – *Brachythops wuestneii* (Konow, 1885)
Carex paniculata Jusl. – *Eutomostethus punctatus* (Konow, 1887)
Carex vesicaria L. – *Macrophya duodecimpunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Carpinus L. – *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758
Carpinus betulus L. – *Fenusia pusilla* (Lepeletier, 1823)*, *Pamphilius marginatus* (Lepeletier, 1823)
Cerasus avium Mönch – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758)*
Cerasus vulgaris Mill. – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)*, *Priophorus pallipes* (Audinet-Serville, 1823)*
Chenopodium L. – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
Chenopodium album L. – *Ametastegia equiseti* (Fallén, 1808)
Chondrilla juncea L. – *Tenthredo costata* Klug, 1817
Cichorium intybus L. – *Tenthredo trabeata* Klug, 1817
Circaea lutetiana L. – *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817
Cirsium vulgare Mill. – *Protemphytus tener* (Fallén, 1808)
Clematis alpina (L.) Mill. – *Pseudodineura clematidis* (Hering, 1924)
Clematis integrifolia L. – *Sterigmos sanguinicollis* (Mocsáry, 1880)
Clematis recta L. – *Pseudodineura clematidisrectae* (Hering, 1924), *Sterigmos ventralis* (Panzer, 1799)
Clematis vitalba L. – *Monophadnus spinolae* (Klug, 1814), *Sterigmos ventralis* (Panzer, 1799)
Comarum palustre L. – *Cladius difformis* (Panzer, 1799)

- Cornus sanguinea** L. – *Emphytus melanarius* (Klug, 1818)
- Corylus** L. – *Emphytus cingulatus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Hemichroa crocea* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Corylus avellana** L. – *Emphytus coryli* Stritt, 1937, *Eriocampa ovata* (Linnaeus, 1781)*, *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pamphilius marginatus* (Lepelletier, 1823), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo fagi* Panzer, 1798, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758
- Cotoneaster** Medic. – *Neurotoma saltuum* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Crataegus** L. – *Arge ustulata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Caliroa plagiata* (Klug, 1814), *Dineura testaceipes* (Klug, 1816), *Hoplocampa crataegi* (Klug, 1816), *Hoplocampa plagiata* (Klug, 1816), *Macrophya punctumalbum* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Neurotoma saltuum* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Palaeocimbex quadrimaculatus* (Müller, 1768), *Pamphilius sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Priophorus pilicornis* (Curtis, 1823), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Trichiosoma tibiale* (Stephens, 1835)
- Crataegus laevigata** (Poir.) DC. – *Dineura stilata* (Klug, 1816), *Hoplocampa pectoralis* (Thomson, 1871)
- Crataegus monogyna** Jacq. – *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Crepis biennis** L. – *Tenthredo trabeata* Klug, 1817
- Cydonia oblonga** Mill. – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Cyperaceae** – *Dolerus asper* Zaddach, 1859, *Dolerus megapterus* Cameron, 1881, *Dolerus possilensis* Cameron, 1882, *Macrophya duodecimpunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Tenthredopsis friesei* (Konow, 1884)
- Dactylis** L. – *Tenthredopsis tessellata* (Klug, 1817)
- Dactylis glomerata** L. – *Tenthredo maculata* Geoffroy, 1785, *Tenthredopsis litterata* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredopsis scutellaris* (Fabricius, 1804), *Tenthredopsis sordida* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis tischbeinii* (Frivaldsky, 1876)
- Daucus carota** L. – *Machrophya chrysur*a (Klug, 1817)
- Deschampsia** P. B. – *Dolerus nitens* Zaddach, 1859
- Deschampsia caespitosa** (L.) P. B. – *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredopsis tessellata* (Klug, 1817)
- Deschampsia flexuosa** (L.) Trin. – *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Dicentra spectabilis** (L.) Lem. – *Sciapteryx consobrina* (Klug, 1816)
- Digitalis grandiflora** Mill. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pachyprotasis variegata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Digitalis purpurea** L. – *Pachyprotasis variegata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Diplotaxis tenuifolia** (L.) DC. – *Athalia glabricollis* (Thomson, 1870)
- Doronicum austriacum** Jacq. – *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)

- Dryopteris Adans.** – *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912)
- Dryopteris filix-mas (L.) Rich.** – *Aneugmenus coronatus* (Klug, 1818), *Blasticotoma filiceti* Klug, 1834, *Stromboceros delicatulus* (Fallén, 1808), *Strongylogaster lineata* (Christ, 1791)
- Dryopteris dilatata (Hoffm.) A. Gray** – *Thrinax maculata* (Klug, 1817)
- Eleocharis palustris (L.) R. et Sch.** – *Dolerus anticus* Klug, 1818
- Elymus Desv.** – *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredopsis sordida* (Klug, 1817)
- Elytrigia intermedia (Host) Nevski** – *Tenthredopsis stigma* (Fabricius, 1798)
- Elytrigia repens (L.) Nevski** – *Calameuta filiformis* (Eversmann, 1847), *Dolerus subalatus* Kerenszky, 1926
- Epilobium L.** – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Epilobium angustifolium L.** – *Aglaostigma langei* (Konow, 1894), *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Epilobium palustre L.** – *Aglaostigma langei* (Konow, 1894)
- Equisetum L.** – *Dolerus aericeps* Thomson, 1871, *Dolerus bimaculatus* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Dolerus germanicus* (Fabricius, 1775), *Dolerus gessneri* Ed. André, 1880, *Dolerus melanopterus* Konow, 1888, *Dolerus pratensis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Dolerus yukonensis* Norton, 1872
- Equisetum fluviatile L. em. Ehrh.** – *Dolerus cothurnatus* Lepelletier, 1823
- Equisetum palustre L.** – *Dolerus cothurnatus* Lepelletier, 1823, *Loderus eversmanni* (Kirby, 1882), *Loderus vestigialis* (Klug, 1818)
- Equisetum pratense Ehrh.** – *Loderus pratorum* (Fallén, 1808)
- Equisetum sylvaticum L.** – *Loderus vestigialis* (Klug, 1818)
- Eriophorum latifolium Hoppe.** – *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Erysimum L.** – *Athalia glabricollis* (Thomson, 1870)
- Euphorbia L.** – *Macrophya annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Euphorbia cyparissias L.** – *Macrophya teutona* (Panzer, 1799), *Tenthredo solitaria* Scopoli, 1763
- Fagus sylvatica L.** – *Abia fagi* Zaddach, 1863, *Caliroa annulipes* (Klug, 1816), *Tremex fuscicornis* (Fabricius, 1787), *Tremex magus* (Fabricius, 1787)
- Festuca L.** – *Dolerus ciliatus* Konow, 1891
- Festuca pratensis Huds.** – *Tenthredopsis scutellaris* (Fallén, 1804)
- Ficaria verna Huds.** – *Sciapteryx consobrina* (Klug, 1816)
- Filipendula Mill.** – *Hartigia xanthostoma* (Eversmann, 1847), *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776
- Filipendula ulmaria (L.) Maxim.** – *Aglaostigma alpinum* (Thomson, 1871), *Aglaostigma nebulosum* (Ed. André, 1881), *Arge ciliaris* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Cladius difformis* (Panzer, 1799), *Claremontia tenuicornis* (Klug, 1816),

- Emphytus calceatus* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus truncatus* Klug, 1818, *Empria alector* Benson, 1938, *Empria baltica* Conde, 1940, *Empria pumila* (Konow, 1896), *Monophadnoides geniculatus* (Hartig, 1837), *Protemphytus tener* (Fallén, 1808), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Fragaria L.** – *Cladius difformis* (Panzer, 1799), *Claremontia confusa* (Konow, 1886), *Emphytus calceatus* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus cinctus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Emphytus cingulatus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Emphytus rufocinctus* (Retzius, 1783), *Macrophya postica* (Brullé, 1832), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Fragaria vesca L.** – *Emphytus truncatus* Klug, 1818, *Empria liturata* (Gmelin, 1790), *Macrophya militaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Fragaria viridis Duch.** – *Macrophya diversipes* (Schrank, 1782), *Macrophya militaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Frangula alnus Mill.** – *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Fraxinus L.** – *Aglaostigma nebulosum* (Ed. André, 1881), *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis simulans* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tomostethus nigritus* (Fallén, 1808), *Urocerus gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Fraxinus excelsior L.** – *Macrophya punctumalbum* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783, *Tomostethus nigritus* (Fabricius, 1804)*
- Fraxinus ornus L.** – *Periclista lineolata* (Klug, 1816)*, *Tomostethus melanopygius* (Costa, 1859)
- Fuchsia Lam.** – *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817
- Galeopsis L.** – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Galeopsis ladanum L.** – *Macrophya sanguinolenta* (Gmelin, 1790), *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Galeopsis speciosa Mill.** – *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Galeopsis tetrahit L.** – *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Galium aparine L.** – *Aglaostigma aucupariae* (Klug, 1817), *Aglaostigma nebulosum* (Ed. André, 1881), *Halidamia affinis* (Fallén, 1807)
- Galium mollugo L.** – *Aglaostigma aucupariae* (Klug, 1817), *Aglaostigma fulvipes* (Scopoli, 1763), *Halidamia affinis* (Fallén, 1807)
- Galium verum L.** – *Aglaostigma aucupariae* (Klug, 1817), *Aglaostigma fulvipes* (Scopoli, 1763)
- Genista germanica L.** – *Rhogogaster genistae* Benson, 1947, *Rhogogaster picta* (Klug, 1817)
- Genista tinctoria L.** – *Rhogogaster genistae* Benson, 1947, *Rhogogaster picta* (Klug, 1817)
- Geranium L.** – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859

- Geranium columbium* L. – *Fenella minuta* (Thomson, 1870)
Geranium phaeum L. – *Macrophya carinthiaca* (Klug, 1817), *Macrophya tenella* Mocsáry, 1881
Geranium pratense L. – *Macrophya carinthiaca* (Klug, 1817), *Prottemphytus carpini* (Hartig, 1837)
Geranium robertianum L. – *Cuneala koehleri* (Klug, 1817), *Prottemphytus carpini* (Hartig, 1837)
Geranium sanguineum L. – *Cuneala koehleri* (Klug, 1817), *Macrophya carinthiaca* (Klug, 1817), *Macrophya tenella* Mocsáry, 1881, *Prottemphytus carpini* (Hartig, 1837)
Geranium sylvaticum L. – *Cuneala koehleri* (Klug, 1817), *Corynis obscura* (Fabricius, 1775), *Fenella monilicornis* Thomson, 1871, *Macrophya albipuncta* (Fallén, 1808), *Macrophya carinthiaca* (Klug, 1817), *Macrophya tenella* Mocsáry, 1881, *Prottemphytus carpini* (Hartig, 1837)
Geum L. – *Empria klugi* (Stephens, 1835), *Empria liturata* (Gmelin, 1790), *Pachyprotasis nigronotata* (Kriechbaumer, 1874)
Geum urbanum L. – *Claremontia waldheimii* (Gimmerthal, 1847), *Metallus gei* (Brischke, 1883), *Monophadnoides geniculatus* (Hartig, 1837)
Glechoma hederacea L. – *Athalia circularis* (Klug, 1815)
Glyceria R. Br. – *Selandria sixii* Vollenhoven, 1858
Glyceria fluitans (L.) R. Br. – *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817)
Helleborus L. – *Monophadnus longicornis* Hartig, 1837
Hepatica nobilis Mill. – *Pseudodineura mentiens* (Thomson, 1871)
Heracleum L. – *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912), *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817
Hieracium L. – *Tenthredo rossii* (Panzer, 1804)
Hypericum L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Hypericum maculatum Cr. – *Tenthredo amoena* Gravenhorst, 1807, *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817
Hypericum perforatum L. – *Tenthredo amoena* Gravenhorst, 1807, *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo zona* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo zonula* Klug, 1817
Holcus L. – *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Hordeum L. – *Trachelus tabidus* (Fabricius, 1775)
Impatiens L. – *Tenthredo trabeata* Klug, 1817
Impatiens glandulifera Royle. – *Siobla sturmii* (Klug, 1817)
Impatiens noli-tangere L. – *Aglaostigma nebulosum* (Ed. André, 1881), *Siobla sturmii* (Klug, 1817)
Iris germanica L. – *Rhadinoceraea reitteri* Konow, 1890
Iris pseudacorus L. – *Rhadinoceraea micans* (Klug, 1816)
Iris pumila L. – *Rhadinoceraea reitteri* Konow, 1890
Iris spuria L. – *Rhadinoceraea micans* (Klug, 1816)
Isatis tinctoria L. – *Elinora flava* (Gmelin, 1790)

- Jasminum L.** – *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Juncus L.** – *Dolerus ferrugatus* Lepeletier, 1823, *Dolerus haematodes* (Schrank, 1781), *Dolerus madidus* Klug, 1818, *Dolerus triplicatus* Klug, 1818, *Dolerus uliginosus* Klug, 1818, *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793), *Selandria sixii* Vollenhoven, 1858, *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis friesei* (Konow, 1884)
- Juncus effusus L.** – *Eutomostethus luteiventris* (Klug, 1816)
- Juncus gerardi Lois** – *Dolerus taeniatus* Zaddach, 1859
- Juniperus communis L.** – *Monoctenus juniperi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Monoctenus obscuratus* (Hartig, 1837)
- Knautia arvensis (L.) Coult.** – *Abia sericea* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Macrophya erythrocnema* Costa, 1859, *Macrophya recognata* Zombori, 1979
- Lamium L.** – *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758
- Lamium album L.** – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Lapsana communis L.** – *Tenthredo trabeata* Klug, 1817
- Larix decidua Mill.** – *Acantholyda laricis* (Giraud, 1861), *Cephalcia alpina* (Klug, 1808), *Janus luteipes* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Sirex juvencus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Urocercus gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Laserpitium latifolium L.** – *Megalodontes klugii* (Leach, 1817)
- Lathyrus pratensis L.** – *Aprosthemella melanurum* (Klug, 1814)
- Lathyrus tuberosus L.** – *Aprosthemella melanurum* (Klug, 1814)
- Laurus nobilis L.** – *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Lembotropis nigricans (L.) Griseb.** – *Rhogogaster picta* (Klug, 1817)
- Leontodon hispidus L.** – *Pachyprotasis variegata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Lepidium draba L.** – *Tenthredo distinguenda* (R. Stein, 1885)
- Lepidium sativum L.** – *Athalia lugens* (Klug, 1813)
- Ligustrum vulgare L.** – *Macrophya punctumalbum* (Linnaeus 1767), *Tenthredo temula* Scopoli, 1763, *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Lilium martagon L.** – *Rhadinoceraea benesi* Beneš, 1961, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Linum catharticum L.** – *Rhogogaster chambersi* Benson, 1947
- Lolium L.** – *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793), *Tenthredopsis tessellata* (Klug, 1817)
- Lolium perenne L.** – *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1917), *Tenthredopsis nassata* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredopsis sordida* (Klug, 1817)
- Lonicera L.** – *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Zaraea aenea* (Klug, 1829), *Zaraea aurulenta* Sichel, 1856
- Lonicera caprifolium L.** – *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Lonicera periclymenum L.** – *Zaraea mutica* Thomson, 1871
- Lonicera tatarica L.** – *Zaraea fasciata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Zaraea mutica* Thomson, 1871
- Lonicera xylosteum L.** – *Hoplocampoides xylostei* (Giraud, 1863), *Zaraea fasciata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Zaraea mutica* Thomson, 1871
- Lotus corniculatus L.** – *Tenthredo nitidior* (Konow, 1888)

- Lycopus* L. – *Pachyprotasis nigronotata* (Kriechbaumer, 1874), *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793, *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912)
- Lycopus europaeus* L. – *Athalia circularis* (Klug, 1815), *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Athalia scutellariae* Cameron, 1880, *Macrophya duodecimpunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817)
- Lysimachia nummularia* L. – *Monostegia abdominalis* (Fabricius, 1798)
- Lysimachia vulgaris* L. – *Monostegia abdominalis* (Fabricius, 1798)
- Lythrum* L. – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Lythrum salicaria* L. – *Ametastegia equiseti* (Fallén, 1808), *Arge fuscipennis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1833)
- Malus domestica* Borkh. – *Hoplocampa testudinea* (Klug, 1816)
- Melissa officinalis* L. – *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793
- Mentha* L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Mentha aquatica* L. – *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis nigronotata* (Kriechbaumer, 1874), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Mentha longifolia* (L.) Nath. – *Tenthredo cunyi* Konow, 1836
- Mentha piperita* L. – *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793
- Menyanthes trifoliata* L. – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817
- Mespilus germanica* L. – *Neurotoma saltuum* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Mycelis muralis* (L.) Wallr. – *Tenthredo trabeata* Klug, 1817
- Myosotis palustris* (L.) Nath. – *Birka cinereipes* (Klug, 1816), *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817
- Nardus stricta* L. – *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817)
- Ocimum basilicum* L. – *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793
- Onoclea struthiopteris* (L.) Roth – *Blasticotoma filiceti* Klug, 1834, *Heptamelus ochroleucus* (Stephens, 1835), *Heterarthrus struthiopteridis* (Forsius, 1910), *Stromboceros delicatulus* (Fallén, 1808), *Thrinax struthiopteridis* Malaise, 1931
- Origanum vulgare* L. – *Macrophya annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Macrophya militaris* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793, *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo temula* Scopoli, 1763
- Padus avium* Mill. – *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Pedicularis palustris* L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Petasites* Mill. – *Tenthredo bipunctula* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo cunyi* Konow, 1836, *Tenthredo procera* Klug, 1817
- Petasites albus* (L.) Gärt. – *Aglaostigma discolor* (Klug, 1817), *Aglaostigma lichtwardti* (Konow, 1892), *Tenthredo mandibularis* Fabricius, 1804
- Petasites hybridus* (L.) G. M. Sch. – *Aglaostigma discolor* (Klug, 1817), *Aglaostigma lichtwardti* (Konow, 1892), *Tenthredo mandibularis* Fabricius, 1804

- Peucedanum alsaticum* L. – *Megalodontes plagiocephalus* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Peucedanum cervaria* (L.) Lap. – *Megalodontes cephalotes* (Fabricius, 1781),
Megalodontes klugii (Leach, 1817)
- Phalaris* L. – *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793)
- Phleum pratense* L. – *Cephus cultratus* Eversmann, 1847
- Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Steud. – *Calameuta filiformis* (Eversmann, 1847)
- Picea abies* (L.) Karst – *Cephalcia abietis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Cephalcia arvensis* Panzer, 1805, *Cephalcia erythrogastra* (Hartig, 1837), *Gilpinia abieticola* (Dalla Torre, 1894), *Gilpinia hercyniae* (Hartig, 1837), *Gilpinia polytoma* (Hartig, 1834), *Sirex noctilio* Fabricius, 1773, *Urocerus gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Pimpinella major* (L.) Huds. – *Tenthredo thomsoni* (Curtis, 1839)
- Pinus* L. – *Acantholyda flaviceps* (Retzius, 1783), *Acantholyda hieroglyphica* (Christ, 1791), *Caenolyda reticulata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Diprion similis* (Hartig, 1834), *Gilpinia socia* (Klug, 1812), *Neodiprion sertifer* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Pinus cembra* L. – *Acantholyda pumilionis* (Giraud, 1861), *Xyela obscura* (Strobl, 1895)
- Pinus mugo* Turra – *Acantholyda pumilionis* (Giraud, 1861), *Xyela obscura* (Strobl, 1895)
- Pinus sylvestris* L. – *Acantholyda posticalis* Matsumura, 1912, *Diprion pini* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Gilpinia laricis* (Jurine, 1807), *Gilpinia pallida* (Klug, 1812), *Gilpinia virens* (Klug, 1812), *Macrodipteron nemoralis* (Enslin, 1917), *Microdipteron pallipes* (Fallén, 1808), *Pleroneura coniferarum* (Hartig, 1837), *Pleroneura dahli* (Hartig, 1837), *Sirex juvencus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Urocerus gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Xyela curva* Benson, 1938, *Xyela graeca* Stein, 1876, *Xyela julii* (Brébisson, 1818), *Xyela longula* Dalman, 1819
- Pinus strobus* L. – *Acantholyda erythrocephala* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Plantago* L. – *Ametastegia equiseti* (Fallén, 1808), *Athalia circularis* (Klug, 1815), *Athalia cordata* Lepeletier, 1823, *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pachyprotasis variegata* (Fallén, 1808), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793, *Tenthredo obsoleta* Klug, 1817
- Plantago lanceolata* L. – *Tenthredo omissa* (Förster, 1844)
- Plantago major* L. – *Pachyprotasis nigronotata* (Kriechbaumer, 1874), *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817
- Plantago media* L. – *Tenthredo omissa* (Förster, 1844)
- Poaceae** – *Dolerus aeneus* Hartig, 1837, *Dolerus anthracinus* Klug, 1818, *Dolerus asper* Zaddach, 1859, *Dolerus gonager* (Fabricius, 1781), *Dolerus liogaster* Thomson, 1871, *Dolerus niger* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Dolerus nigratus* (Müller, 1776), *Dolerus picipes* Klug, 1818, *Dolerus possilensis* Cameron, 1882, *Dolerus puncticollis* Thomson, 1871, *Dolerus sanguinicollis* Klug, 1818, *Macrophya duodecimpunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Monophadnus monticola* Hartig, 1837, *Tenthredo maculata* Geoffroy, 1785

- Poa L.** – *Atomostethus ephippium* (Panzer, 1798), *Dolerus haematodes* (Schrank, 1781), *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793), *Selandria sixii* Vollenhoven, 1858
- Poa pratensis L.** – *Cephus nigrinus* Thomson, 1871, *Tenthredopsis coquebertii* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredopsis scutellaris* (Fallén, 1804)
- Polygonatum multiflorum (L.) All.** – *Phymatocera aterrima* (Klug, 1816)
- Polygonatum odoratum (Mill.) Druce** – *Phymatocera aterrima* (Klug, 1816)
- Polygonum aviculare L.** – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Polygonum bistorta L.** – *Tenthredo velox* Fabricius, 1798
- Polygonum persicaria L.** – *Ametastegia equiseti* (Fallén, 1808), *Protemphytus perla* (Klug, 1818), *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Polypodium vulgare L.** – *Heptamelus ochroleucus* (Stephens, 1835), *Stromboceros delicatulus* (Fallén, 1808)
- Polystichum Roth.** – *Blasticotoma filiceti* Klug, 1834, *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776
- Populus L.** – *Abia lutea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pamphilius betulae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Protemphytus perla* (Klug, 1818), *Pseudoclavellaria amerinae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Urocercus gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Xiphydria longicollis* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Xiphydria prolongata* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Populus alba L.** – *Heterarthrus ochropoda* (Klug, 1818), *Messa glaucopis* (Konow, 1907)
- Populus balsamifera L.** – *Trichiocampus grandis* (Audinet-Serville, 1823)
- Populus canadensis Mönch** – *Messa hortulana* (Klug, 1818)*
- Populus × canescens (Ait.) Sm.** – *Heterarthrus ochropoda* (Klug, 1818)*, *Messa glaucopis* (Konow, 1907)
- Populus nigra L.** – *Heterarthrus ochropoda* (Klug, 1818), *Janus luteipes* (Lepeletier, 1823), *Messa glaucopis* (Konow, 1907), *Messa hortulana* (Klug, 1818), *Tremex fuscicornis* (Fabricius, 1787), *Trichiocampus grandis* (Audinet-Serville, 1823)
- Populus nigra var. italica Du Roi** – *Fenusa pusilla* (Lepeletier, 1823)*
- Populus tremula L.** – *Ametastegia albipes* (Thomson, 1871), *Caliroa tremulae* (Chevin, 1974), *Caliroa varipes* (Klug, 1816), *Heterarthrus ochropoda* (Klug, 1818), *Messa glaucopis* (Konow, 1907), *Pamphilius histrio* Latreille, 1812, *Pamphilius latifrons* (Fallén, 1808), *Trichiocampus aeneus* (Zaddach, 1859), *Trichiocampus grandis* (Audinet-Serville, 1823), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Rhogogaster viridis* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Potentilla L.** – *Cladius difformis* (Panzer, 1799), *Fenella* sp.*, *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859

- Potentilla arenaria Borkh.** – *Fenella arenariae* Zombori, 1978, *Fenella judaica* (Forsius, 1930), *Fenella nigrita* Westwood, 1839*
- Potentilla recta L.** – *Emphytus truncatus* Klug, 1818
- Potentilla reptans L.** – *Fenella nigrita* Westwood, 1840, *Macrophya annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Macrophya diversipes* (Schrank, 1782), *Macrophya militaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Prenanthes purpurea L.** – *Tenthredo trabeata* Klug, 1817
- Prunus L.** – *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776
- Prunus armeniaca L.** – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Prunus domestica L.** – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Hoplocampa flava* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Hoplocampa minuta* (Christ, 1791), *Neurotoma nemoralis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Neurotoma saltuum* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804)
- Prunus spinosa L.** – *Hoplocampa chrysorrhoea* (Klug, 1816), *Hoplocampa flava* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Hoplocampa rutilicornis* (Klug, 1814), *Neurotoma nemoralis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Palaeocimbex quadrimaculatus* (Müller, 1766), *Pamphilius sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pareophora pruni* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Sterictiphora furcata* (Villers, 1799)
- Pteridium aquilinum (L.) Kuhn.** – *Aneugmenus padi* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Aneugmenus temporalis* (Thomson, 1871), *Atoposelandria fuerstenbergensis* (Konow, 1885), *Blasticotoma filiceti* Klug, 1834, *Pseudotaxonus filicis* (Klug, 1817), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Stromboceros delicatulus* (Fallén, 1808), *Strongylogaster lineata* (Christ, 1791), *Strongylogaster xanthocera* Stephens, 1835, *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo fagi* Panzer, 1798, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Thrinax maculata* (Klug, 1817), *Thrinax mixta* (Klug, 1817)
- Pulsatilla Adans.** – *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817
- Pulsatilla grandis Wender.** – *Pseudodineura parvula* (Klug, 1816)
- Pulsatilla patens (L.) Mill.** – *Pseudodineura parvula* (Klug, 1816)
- Pyrus communis L.** – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758)*, *Hoplocampa brevis* (Klug, 1816), *Janus compressus* (Fabricius, 1793), *Neurotoma saltuum* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Palaeocimbex quadrimaculatus* (Müller, 1766), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Tremex magus* (Fabricius, 1787), *Xiphydria longicollis* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Quercus L.** – *Allantus togatus* (Panzer, 1801), *Apethymus braccatus* (Gmelin, 1790), *Arge rustica* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Caliroa annulipes* (Klug, 1816), *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Caliroa cinxia* (Klug, 1816), *Caliroa varipes* (Klug, 1816), *Harpiphorus lepidus* (Klug, 1818), *Janus femoratus* (Curtis, 1830), *Macrophya punctumalbum* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Neurotoma mandibularis* (Zaddach, 1866), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pamphilius sylvarum*

- (Stephens, 1835), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Tremex magus* (Fabricius, 1787), *Xiphydria longicollis* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Quercus cerris* L.** – *Apethymus abdominalis cerris* (Kollar, 1850), *Apethymus ustus* (Klug, 1818)
- Quercus frainetto* Ten.** – *Profenusa pygmaea* (Klug, 1816)*
- Quercus petraea* (Mattuschka) Lieblein** – *Caliroa cinxia* (Klug, 1816)*, *Periclista albida* (Klug, 1816), *Periclista lineolata* (Klug, 1816), *Periclista pubescens* (Zaddach, 1859), *Profenusa pygmaea* (Klug, 1816)
- Quercus pubescens* Willd.** – *Profenusa pygmaea* (Klug, 1816)*
- Quercus robur* L.** – *Apethymus abdominalis* (Lepelletier, 1823), *Dineura opaca* (Fabricius, 1775), *Harpiphorus lepidus* (Klug, 1818)*, *Periclista albida* (Klug, 1816), *Periclista lineolata* (Klug, 1814), *Periclista pubescens* (Zaddach, 1859), *Profenusa pygmaea* (Klug, 1816)
- Ranunculus* L.** – *Corynis crassicornis* (Rossi, 1790), *Macrophya albipuncta* (Fallén, 1808), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912), *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817
- Ranunculus acris* L.** – *Monophadnus pallescens* (Gmelin, 1790), *Pseudodineura fuscula* (Klug, 1816), *Sciapteryx costalis* (Fabricius, 1775), *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817
- Ranunculus lanuginosus* L.** – *Pseudodineura fuscula* (Klug, 1816)
- Ranunculus polyanthemos* L.** – *Pseudodineura fuscula* (Klug, 1816)*
- Ranunculus repens* L.** – *Monophadnus pallescens* (Gmelin, 1790), *Pseudodineura fuscula* (Klug, 1816), *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Ranunculus sceleratus* L.** – *Stethomostus fuliginosus* (Schrank, 1781)
- Raphanus raphanistrum* L.** – *Athalia glabricollis* (Thomson, 1870), *Athalia lugens* (Klug, 1813), *Elinora flava* (Gmelin, 1790)
- Rheum* L.** – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Ribes* L.** – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Ribes nigrum* L.** – *Janus compressus* (Fabricius, 1793)
- Ribes rubrum* L.** – *Eriocampa dorpatica* (Konow, 1887), *Hoplocampa chrysorrhoea* (Klug, 1816), *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Ribes uva-crispa* L.** – *Hoplocampa chrysorrhoea* (Klug, 1816)
- Rorippa amphibia* (L.) Bess.** – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Rosa* L.** – *Ardis brunniventris* (Hartig, 1837), *Ardis sulcata* (Cameron, 1882), *Arge enodis* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Arge gracilicornis* (Klug, 1814), *Arge nigripes* (Retzius, 1783), *Arge ochropus* (Gmelin, 1790), *Arge pagana* (Panzer, 1798), *Blennocampa pusilla* (Klug, 1816), *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Cladardis elongatula* (Klug, 1817), *Cladius pectinicornis* (Geoffroy, 1785)*, *Emphytus basalis* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus calceatus* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus cingulatus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Emphytus coryli* Stritt, 1937, *Emphytus didymus* (Klug, 1818),

- Emphytus truncatus* Klug, 1818, *Macrophya diversipes* (Schrank, 1782), *Macrophya militaris* (Klug, 1817), *Monardis plana* (Klug, 1817), *Pamphilius balteatus* (Fallén, 1808), *Pamphilius inanitus* (Villers, 1789), *Pamphilius stramineipes* (Hartig, 1837), *Sterictiphora geminata* (Gmelin, 1790), *Syrista parreysii* (Spinola, 1843), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Rosa agrestis** Savi. – *Emphytus balteatus* Klug, 1818
- Rosa arvensis** Huds. – *Apethymus serotinus* (Müller, 1776), *Emphytus balteatus* Klug, 1818, *Endelomyia aethiops* (Fabricius, 1781)
- Rosa canina** L. – *Arge* sp.*, *Arge ochropus* (Gmelin, 1790)*, *Arge pagana* (Panzer, 1798)*, *Blennocampa pusilla* (Klug, 1816)*, *Cladardis elongatula* (Klug, 1817)*, *Cladius pectinicornis* (Geoffroy, 1785)*, *Emphytus balteatus* Klug, 1818, *Endelomyia aethiops* (Fabricius, 1781), *Macrophya annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817)
- Rosa gallica** L. – *Allantus viennensis* (Schrank, 1781), *Apethymus serotinus* (Müller, 1776), *Arge enodis* (Linnaeus, 1767)*, *Blennocampa pusilla* (Klug, 1816)*, *Emphytus balteatus* Klug, 1818
- Rosa multiflora** Thunb. – *Apethymus serotinus* (Müller, 1776), *Cladius pectinicornis* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Rosa pendulina** L. – *Allantus viennensis* (Schrank, 1781), *Apethymus serotinus* (Müller, 1776), *Emphytus balteatus* Klug, 1818
- Rosa rubiginosa** L. – *Allantus viennensis* (Schrank, 1781), *Apethymus serotinus* (Müller, 1776), *Emphytus balteatus* Klug, 1818
- Rosa spinosissima** L. – *Allantus viennensis* (Schrank, 1781), *Apethymus serotinus* (Müller, 1776), *Emphytus cinctus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Emphytus rufocinctus* (Retzius, 1783)
- Rubus** L. – *Arge cyanocrocea* (Forster, 1771), *Emphytus calceatus* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus cinctus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Macrophya annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Macrophya postica* (Brullé, 1832), *Metallus pumilus* (Klug, 1816)*, *Monophadnoides geniculatus* (Hartig, 1837), *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912)
- Rubus caesius** L. – *Macrophya montana* (Scopoli, 1763), *Macrophya rufipes* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Metallus pumilus* (Klug, 1816), *Perineura rubi* (Panzer, 1805)
- Rubus fruticosus** agg. – *Macrophya blanda* (Fabricius, 1775), *Macrophya diversipes* (Schrank, 1782), *Macrophya montana* (Scopoli, 1763), *Metallus albipes* (Cameron, 1875), *Metallus pumilus* (Klug, 1816), *Monophadnoides ruficruris* (Brullé, 1832), *Priophorus brullei* Dahlbom, 1835
- Rubus idaeus** L. – *Arge gracilicornis* (Klug, 1814), *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Claremontia alternipes* (Klug, 1816), *Empria longicornis* (Thomson, 1871), *Empria tridens* (Konow, 1896), *Hartigia nigra* (Harris, 1776), *Macrophya blanda* (Fabricius, 1775), *Macrophya militaris* (Klug, 1817), *Metallus albipes* (Cameron, 1875), *Metallus pumilus* (Klug, 1816), *Pachyprotasis antennata*

- (Klug, 1817), *Pamphilius hortorum* (Klug, 1808), *Perineura rubi* (Panzer, 1805), *Priophorus brullei* Dahlbom, 1835, *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Sterictiphora furcata* (Villers, 1799), *Taxonus agrorum* (Fallén, 1808)
- Rubus saxatilis L.** – *Metallus pumilus* (Klug, 1816), *Priophorus brullei* Dahlbom, 1835
- Rumex L.** – *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Rumex acetosella L.** – *Ametastegia equiseti* (Fallén, 1808)
- Rumex crispus L.** – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Salix L.** – *Allantus togatus* (Panzer, 1801), *Ametastegia albipes* (Thomson, 1871), *Arge clavicornis* Fabricius, 1781, *Arge ustulata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Caliroa annulipes* (Klug, 1816), *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pseudoclavellaria amerinae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Trichiosoma latreillei* Leach, 1817, *Trichiosoma vitellinae* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Xiphydria prolongata* (Geoffroy, 1785)
- Salix alba L.** – *Abia lutea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Empria immersa* (Klug, 1818), *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Salix aurita L.** – *Caloria varipes* (Klug, 1814), *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1816)*, *Pamphilius gyllenhali* (Dahlbom, 1835), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo velox* Fabricius, 1798
- Salix caprea L.** – *Abia lutea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818), *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pamphilius gyllenhali* (Dahlbom, 1835), *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Scolioneura tirolensis* Enslin, 1914, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758, *Trichiocampus aeneus* (Zaddach, 1859), *Trichiocampus grandis* (Audinet-Serville, 1823)
- Salix cinerea L.** – *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818)*
- Salix daphnoides Vill.** – *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818)
- Salix fragilis L.** – *Arge melanochoa* (Gmelin, 1790), *Caliroa annulipes* (Klug, 1816)*, *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818)*
- Salix pentandra L.** – *Trichiocampus aeneus* (Zaddach, 1859)
- Salix purpurea L.** – *Arge enodis* (Linnaeus, 1767)*, *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Salix triandra L.** – *Arge enodis* (Linnaeus, 1767)*, *Trichiocampus aeneus* (Zaddach, 1859)
- Salix viminalis L.** – *Empria immersa* (Klug, 1818), *Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818), *Messa wuestneii* (Konow, 1894), *Protemythys perla* (Klug, 1818)
- Salvia nemorosa L.** – *Melanopus fabricii* (Leach, 1817)
- Sambucus L.** – *Macrophya annulata* (Geoffroy, 1785)

- Sambucus ebulus* L. – *Macrophya albicincta* (Schrank, 1776), *Macrophya alboannulata* Costa, 1859, *Macrophya crassula* (Klug, 1817), *Macrophya ribis* (Schrank, 1781)
- Sambucus nigra* L. – *Macrophya albicincta* (Schrank, 1776), *Macrophya ribis* (Schrank, 1781)
- Sambucus racemosa* L. – *Macrophya albicincta* (Schrank, 1776), *Macrophya alboannulata* Costa, 1859, *Macrophya ribis* (Schrank, 1781), *Zaraea aenea* (Klug, 1829)
- Sanguisorba* L. – *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo colon* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo silensis* Costa, 1859
- Sanguisorba minor* Scop. – *Claremontia puncticeps* (Konow, 1886), *Emphytus didymus* (Klug, 1818)
- Sanguisorba officinalis* L. – *Claremontia puncticeps* (Konow, 1886), *Emphytus calceatus* (Klug, 1818), *Emphytus truncatus* Klug, 1818
- Sarothamnus scoparius* (L.) Wimm. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Rhogogaster genistae* (Benson, 1947), *Rhogogaster picta* (Klug, 1817)
- Scabiosa* L. – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Scirpus* L. – *Selandria sixii* Vollenhoven, 1858
- Scirpus radicans* Schkuhr – *Dolerus haematodes* (Schrank, 1781)
- Scrophularia* L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pachyprotasis simulans* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo rossii* (Panzer, 1804)
- Scrophularia nodosa* L. – *Tenthredo scrophulariae* Linnaeus, 1758
- Scrophularia umbrosa* Dum. – *Tenthredo scrophulariae* Linnaeus, 1758
- Scutellaria galericulata* L. – *Athalia scutellariae* Cameron, 1880
- Secale cereale* L. – *Cephus pygmaeus* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Trachelus tabidus* (Fabricius, 1775), *Trachelus troglodyta* (Fabricius, 1787)
- Sedum* L. – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo ignobilis* Klug, 1817
- Sedum album* L. – *Athalia cornubiae* Benson, 1931
- Senecio* L. – *Pachyprotasis simulans* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Senecio aquaticus* Huds. – *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)
- Senecio fluviatilis* Wallr. – *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)
- Senecio nemorensis* agg. – *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo mioceras* (Enslin, 1912), *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)
- Senecio sylvaticus* L. – *Macrophya sanguinolenta* (Gmelin, 1790), *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)
- Senecio viscosus* L. – *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)
- Serratula tinctoria* L. – *Macrophya parvula* Konow, 1884
- Seseli libanotis* (L.) W. D. J. Koch – *Megalodontes klugii* (Leach, 1817)
- Sinapis* L. – *Athalia lugens* (Klug, 1813)

- Sinapis alba* L. – *Athalia glabricollis* (Thomson, 1870), *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Elinora flava* (Gmelin, 1790)
- Sinapis arvensis* L. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Elinora flava* (Gmelin, 1790)
- Sisymbrium* L. – *Athalia glabricollis* (Thomson, 1870), *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Sisymbrium officinale* (L.) Scop. – *Athalia liberta* (Klug, 1815)
- Solanum* L. – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Solanum tuberosum* L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Solidago* Cass. – *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Solidago virgaurea* L. – *Arge fuscipennis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1833), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pachyprotasis simulans* (Klug, 1817)
- Sonchus arvensis* L. – *Tenthredo neobesa* Zombori, 1980, *Tenthredo rossii* (Panzer, 1804)
- Sorbus* L. – *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pamphilius sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Rhogogaster chlorosoma* (Benson, 1943)
- Sorbus aria* (L.) Cr. – *Hoplocampa ariae* Benson, 1933
- Sorbus aucuparia* L. – *Dineura testaceipes* (Klug, 1816), *Hoplocampa alpina* (Zetterstedt, 1838), *Priophorus brullei* Dahlbom, 1835, *Priophorus compressicornis* (Fabricius, 1804), *Rhogogaster punctulata* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo fagi* Panzer, 1798, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776, *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Trichiosoma sorbi* Hartig, 1840
- Sorbus torminalis* (L.) Cr. – *Dineura stilata* (Klug, 1816)
- Spiraea* L. – *Cladius difformis* (Panzer, 1799), *Monophadnoides geniculatus* (Hartig, 1827), *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Spiraea media* Fr. Schm. – *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo ferruginea* Schrank, 1776
- Spiraea salicifolia* L. – *Tenthredo balteata* Klug, 1817
- Stachys* L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
- Stachys officinalis* (L.) Trevis. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Stellaria* L. – *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817)
- Succisa pratensis* Mönch – *Abia sericea* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
- Symphoricarpos rivularis* Suksdorf – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783, *Zaraea fasciata* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Symphytum officinale* L. – *Tenthredo rubricoxis* (Enslin, 1912)
- Syringa vulgaris* L. – *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783
- Tanacetum vulgare* L. – *Pachyprotasis variegata* (Fallén, 1808)
- Teucrium* L. – *Athalia rufoscutellata* Mocsáry, 1879
- Thalictrum* L. – *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817

- Tilia cordata* Mill. – *Parna tenella* (Klug, 1816)
Tilia platyphyllos Scop. – *Parna tenella* (Klug, 1816)
Trifolium pratense L. – *Tenthredo schaefferi* Klug, 1817
Trifolium repens L. – *Tenthredo arcuata* Forster, 1771, *Tenthredo notha* Klug, 1817, *Tenthredo schaefferi* Klug, 1817
Triticum L. – *Cephus pygmaeus* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Dolerus haematodes* (Schrank, 1781), *Trachelus tabidus* (Fabricius, 1775)
Triticum aestivum L. – *Cephus pygmaeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)*, *Dolerus niger* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Selandria serva* (Fabricius, 1793)
Trollius europaeus L. – *Pseudodineura enslini* (Hering, 1923)
Tropaeolum L. – *Athalia rosae* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Tussilago farfara L. – *Aglaostigma alpinum* (Thomson, 1871), *Aglaostigma discolor* (Klug, 1817), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Tenthredo mandibularis* Fabricius, 1804, *Tenthredo marginella* Fabricius, 1793, *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
Typhoides arundinacea (L.) Dum. – *Calameuta filiformis* (Eversmann, 1847), *Cephus infuscatus* (Thomson, 1871)
Ulmus L. – *Fenusa ulmi* Sundewall, 1844*, *Xiphydria prolongata* (Geoffroy, 1785)
Ulmus laevis Pall. – *Fenusa ulmi* Sundewall, 1844*, *Priophorus rufipes* Audinet-Serville, 1823
Ulmus minor Mill. – *Kaliofenusa ulmi* (Sundevall, 1844), *Priophorus rufipes* Audinet-Serville, 1823, *Priophorus ulmi* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Ulmus procera Salisb. – *Priophorus rufipes* Audinet-Serville, 1823
Ulmus scabra Mill. – *Kaliofenusa ulmi* (Sundevall, 1844)
Urtica L. – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
Urtica dioica L. – *Pachyprotasis antennata* (Klug, 1817)
Vaccinium L. – *Caliroa annulipes* (Klug, 1816)
Valeriana officinalis L. – *Macrophya albicincta* (Schrank, 1776)
Veratrum L. – *Tenthredo moniliata* Klug, 1817
Veratrum album L. – *Veratra nodicornis* (Konow, 1886)
Veratrum nigrum L. – *Veratra nodicornis* (Konow, 1886)
Verbascum L. – *Tenthredo rossii* (Panzer, 1804)
Verbascum nigrum L. – *Tenthredo scrophulariae* Linnaeus, 1758
Verbascum thapsus L. – *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Veronica L. – *Tenthredo mesomela* Linnaeus, 1758
Veronica beccabunga L. – *Athalia bicolor* Lepeletier, 1823, *Athalia circularis* (Klug, 1815), *Pachyprotasis rapae* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Veronica chamaedrys L. – *Macrophya sanguinolenta* (Gmelin, 1790)
Veronica longifolia L. – *Macrophya sanguinolenta* (Gmelin, 1790)
Veronica teucrium L. – *Tenthredo olivacea* Klug, 1817
Viburnum L. – *Janus luteipes* (Lepeletier, 1823)
Viburnum opulus L. – *Macrophya albicincta* (Schrank, 1776), *Rhogogaster scalaris* (Klug, 1817), *Tenthredo livida* Linnaeus, 1758, *Tenthredo vespa* Retzius, 1783

- Vicia L.* – *Tenthredo atra* Linnaeus, 1758
Vicia cracca L. – *Aprothema fusicorne* (Thomson, 1808), *Tenthredo schaefferi* Klug, 1817
Vicia sativa L. – *Aprothema austriacum* (Konow, 1892)
Viola L. – *Ametastegia glabrata* (Fallén, 1808)
Viola canina L. – *Prottemphytus pallipes* (Spinola, 1808)
Viola odorata L. – *Prottemphytus pallipes* (Spinola, 1808)
Viola tricolor L. – *Prottemphytus pallipes* (Spinola, 1808)
Vitis vinifera L. – *Macrophya rufipes* (Linnaeus, 1758)

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